

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (04)

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DOI

10.5281/zenodo.2558454

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Inder Taneja published two papers on Zenodo (combining results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
18-01-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ²⁸
03-02-2019	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20000 to 30000 ²⁹

Authors published four papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁵

Note

Previously, authors used ‘CSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to natural numbers (as originally introduced by Inder Taneja) and ‘NCSR’ to refer to crazy sequential representations that evaluate to negative integers (as introduced by ourselves). Authors always avoided ‘PCSR’ as this might introduce ambiguity (pseudo vs. positive CSR).

From this point forward, authors will use the following:

- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any integer value
- +CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any positive integer
- CSR = Crazy sequential representation, evaluating to any negative integer

Historic Overview Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published two papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 62):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁶
02-02-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to #####) ²⁷

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89_A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$-(1+2+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Aim

Attempt to ‘fill the gaps’ in our previous work ^{6,7,8,12,13,14,15,25} by identifying...

- increasing genuine CSR for integers without any increasing genuine CSR.
- decreasing genuine CSR for integers without any decreasing genuine CSR.

Results

Authors identified 708094 previously unknown genuine CSR, see supplements.

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	124904	184217	135701	263272

Overview

Currently, within the -2147483647 up to 2147483647 range, increasing CSR are available for 1752072 integers, and decreasing CSR are available for 2441622 integers:

	Increasing +CSR	Decreasing +CSR	Increasing -CSR	Decreasing -CSR
Genuine	871588	1215143	868287	1190901
Pseudo	4493	5845	7704	29733
Total	876081	1220988	875991	1220634

Note

Authors consider CSR to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published CSR are the shortest in existence.
- Published CSR are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable CSR do not exists.

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